

The role and importance of cognitive technology in digital economic

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ABSTRACT

It is cognitive technologies that are of great importance in our development of the digital economy. Cognitive technologies help us develop and activate knowledge, experience and decisions. Together with the analysis and implementation of business, the role of cognitive technologies in its development is significantly known.

In general, cognitive technologies are understood as technologies in the scope of rationalizing and forming intelligent systems for the development and activation of knowledge, experience, communication and decisions. In addition, the widely used cognitive technologies develop and implement the principles of organization and operation of natural and artificial intelligent systems. They are a complex of mathematical methods, algorithms and computer technologies that create intelligent software-hardware systems, can determine natural language and form, dynamically study systems, formulate hypotheses, evaluate and solve other issues. One of the main essence of cognitive technologies is to find out how a person processes all the information he receives, including which forms he can create schemas. One of the reasons why cognitive technologies are distinct from cognition is that cognition occurs only in novel environments. In the digital economy, we mainly use cognitive modeling.

Because cognitive modeling has a great role in decision-making when it is complex and uncertain, together with its analysis and systematization. Cognitive modeling helps to better understand the problem situation based on the qualitative analysis of the system. Allows you to identify problems and contradictions specific to the system.

In the digital economy, software occupies more than 40% of the electronic market. There are many electronic products on the market, but no matter how many people buy them, they will not run out. Analyzing them, we can see the great importance of cognitive technologies. Cognitive business analytics (CBA) can be used to support a wide range of business objectives and strategies. In addition, it consists in clearly showing business analyzes and their systematization. Short-term operational solutions such as product placement and competitive pricing have greatly expanded with CBA. Long-term strategies in areas such as brand recognition and market share will be more successful with the forecasting and scene modeling that CBA provides. In business, cognitive technologies are used to ensure goods and their quality, and at the same time increase their storage.

The impact of digital technologies is felt both globally and locally. The digital economy is a rapidly growing part of the global economy as a combination of new production. Today, as a

result of the rapid growth of smart technologies, new aspects of the economy unknown to us are emerging.

Including the emergence of modern professions and the development of new electronic goods. In the markets organized in this way in the digital economy, along with the emergence of new businesses, the analysis of businesses, their systematization and determination of prices and product placement in a competitive environment will further increase the importance of cognitive technologies in the digital economy. The growth of the digital economy is linked to the growth of a number of marketing activities directly related to digital and mobile technologies. At the current stage of technological development and the current state of marketing, the digital economy should be considered not as a goal, but as a means of increasing the efficiency of economic activity.

In conclusion, in today's modern environment, it is precisely in the digital economy that we need to make extensive use of cognitive technologies. This is due to the rapid growth of information communication, which is the basis of the digital economy.

REFERENCES:

1. G'.M. Porsaev, B.Sh. Safarov, D.Q. Usmanova. Raqamli iqtisodiyot asoslari. (Darslik) –T.: «Fan va texnologiyalar nashriyot-matbaa uyi», 2020. 372 b.
- 2.<https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/raqamli-iqtisodiyot-va-texnologiyalarni-rivojlantirish-asoslari?ysclid=lz4fe292qv690742373>
- 3.<https://genderi.org/i-bob-insonning-kognitiv-jarayonlarini-nazariy-tahlil-qilish.html?page=6>

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